

Challenges and Support Systems for Female Workers in Special Circumstances in Vietnam's Industrial Zones

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Abstract

This study examines the unique challenges faced by female workers in special circumstances in Vietnam's industrial and export processing zones, particularly single mothers and those suffering from severe illnesses or occupational diseases. The research methodology includes consultations and interviews with experts, in-depth interviews with affected female workers, and engagement with union officials and employers.

The survey covered a total of 454 respondents, divided into two groups: 245 female workers in special circumstances and 209 union officials. The findings indicate that the most pressing issue for these workers is the lack of adequate housing, as rented accommodations often fail to meet their families' basic needs. Additionally, they encounter significant barriers to accessing healthcare due to high costs and insufficient wages. Low wages also force many workers in industrial zones to borrow money for daily living expenses.

The effectiveness of support provided by the State, enterprises, and trade unions is perceived as inadequate. Despite the existence of support mechanisms, there remains a substantial gap between the needs of these workers and the assistance available, particularly in terms of healthcare and housing. This study underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions to enhance both the material and mental well-being of this vulnerable group. It provides policy recommendations aimed at improving their quality of life through more effective and comprehensive support measures.

Keywords

female union officials and employers, healthcare and housing, in-depth interviews, industrial zones, single mothers, special circumstances, support systems, female workers with health problems

JEL codes: I14, I15, I31

Introduction

In Vietnam, particularly within industrial and export processing zones, female workers in special circumstances – such as single mothers and those suffering from severe illnesses or occupational diseases – constitute a highly vulnerable segment of the labor force. These workers face unique challenges, which are often intensified by their demanding work environments and the high-pressure nature of industrial jobs. Despite increasing recognition of these issues, research specifically addressing the hardships faced by this demographic remains limited.

This study aims to explore the complex realities of these women's lives, identifying the barriers they encounter in relation to labor policies, access to social welfare services, and the support provided by businesses, the government, and non-governmental organizations. By shedding light on these issues, the study emphasizes the urgent need for targeted interventions to improve not only the material conditions of these workers but also their overall well-being. This comprehensive approach aims to provide a deeper insight into the supports necessary to enhance the lives of female workers facing significant hardships in Vietnam.

A comprehensive analysis is conducted to examine the key challenges these women face, including financial instability, limited access to healthcare, and the lack of effective occupational health measures. Additionally, the study assesses the effectiveness of existing support structures, identifying gaps that need to be addressed to better assist this vulnerable group.

Furthermore, this research seeks to contribute to policy discussions by advocating for more robust and effective strategies at both the corporate and governmental levels. These strategies should not only provide immediate financial and healthcare support but also focus on long-term solutions that enhance sustainability and overall quality of life for female workers in industrial zones.

Ultimately, this study aims to drive meaningful change by offering data-driven insights into the challenges faced by female workers in Vietnam's industrial sector. The findings are intended to inform policymakers, business leaders, and social organizations, encouraging them to implement more thoughtful and impactful support systems.

Literature Review

This research focuses on the challenges faced by female workers in two specific circumstances: single mothers and those experiencing health limitations. The study aims to deepen the understanding of the particular struggles these groups encounter by analyzing relevant data and prior studies.

Research on the Lives of Single Mother Workers

This section examines the conditions faced by single mothers, defined by Gucciardi et al. (2004) as women who are unmarried, separated, divorced, or widowed and solely responsible for raising their children. The research further distinguishes between “single mothers from the start” – those who have children independently – and “secondary single mothers” – those who become single after divorce or widowhood (Le Minh Tien 2020). While South Korea has recognized and implemented policies to support single mothers, Vietnam lacks such initiatives, significantly affecting the social and economic well-being of these women.

As divorce rates in Vietnam continue to rise, more women are assuming sole parental responsibilities. Economic hardships are particularly pronounced among single mothers in rural areas, where employment opportunities are limited (Vo Thi Cam Ly 2016). In the labor market, single mothers face additional challenges, including inadequate childcare support, discriminatory employment policies, and, in some regions, exposure to sexual harassment (Bimbashi and Marcic 2015). The COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated these issues, increasing the strain of balancing work and family responsibilities (Hertz et al. 2021).

Financial difficulties and emotional struggles – such as loneliness and depression – are prevalent among single mothers, negatively impacting their social interactions and overall well-being (Kotwal and Prabhakar 2009; Van Gasse and Mortelmans 2020). Gender imbalances in the workplace further hinder their financial stability and social relationships.

Research on the Lives of Female Workers with Health Limitations

Women suffering from severe health issues or disabilities, particularly in developing regions of the Asia-Pacific, frequently face overlooked concerns and violations of their rights due to the intersection of health status, gender, and poverty (Sim 1999). Those who receive employer support often develop stronger ties with their companies; however, many require long-term sick leave, which affects their productivity and places additional stress on their domestic responsibilities (Englund et al. 2016; Dellve and Ahlborg 2012).

Occupational health risks in industries such as electronics and garments are particularly severe. Workers in these sectors frequently suffer from repetitive strain injuries, poor mental health, and illnesses caused by substandard working conditions (Yu et al. 2013; Ahmed and Raihan 2014). The lack of adequate health and safety measures – such as clean facilities and fair wages – further exacerbates these challenges (Akhter et al. 2010).

For migrant female workers, health risks are even more pronounced. Workplace abuses and gender-based inequalities at home contribute to deteriorating mental health and lower job satisfaction (Moyce and Schenker 2018; Deori 2016). Support from colleagues and supervisors is crucial in alleviating these challenges, yet often remains insufficient, leading to prolonged sick leave and declining mental well-being (Sultana et al. 2015).

This research underscores the urgent need for comprehensive social security systems and proactive trade union support to address and mitigate the challenges faced by these vulnerable groups. Practical support measures, such as financial aid and housing assistance provided by trade unions, have proven essential in improving the lives of female workers suffering from severe illnesses or occupational injuries. The study emphasizes the necessity of strengthening access to social security and support systems to ensure that no worker is left behind.

Methods

Employing a mixed-methods approach, this study utilized surveys, expert interviews, and in-depth interviews with female workers in special circumstances, alongside discussions with trade union officials and employers. The survey collected 454 responses, divided into two main groups: 245 female workers facing special circumstances and 209 trade union officials. This approach ensured a comprehensive analysis of the challenges from multiple perspectives. The geographical scope of this research encompassed six provinces and cities

across Vietnam, covering regions in the north, south, and central highlands. This broad coverage provided a diverse overview of the challenges and factors influencing female workers in key industrial zones.

To facilitate data collection, the research team formally sought support from the Federation of Labor in industrial and export processing zones across the selected provinces. Each province designated two to three industrial or export processing zones for participation in the study. Within each chosen zone, two to three industrial businesses were selected, ensuring representation of diverse production sectors.

The authors collaborated with management boards at each firm to compile a list of single mothers and female workers with health issues. Direct interviews were conducted with the selected workers, while additional insights were gathered from trade union representatives in industrial and export processing zones. Following this process, the final sample consisted of 245 female workers, either single mothers or individuals suffering from health conditions.

Results

The current conditions of female workers in special circumstances are summarized in the following table.

Table 1. General overview of female workers in special circumstances within the research sample

Characteristic	Value (N, %)
Current status of female workers	
Single mothers	129 (52.7)
Suffering from severe diseases	112 (45.7)
Both conditions above	4 (1.6)
Educational level	
Elementary school	13 (5.3)
Middle school	81 (33.1)
High school	87 (35.5)
Basic vocational	5 (2.0)
Intermediate vocational	23 (9.4)
College, university	36 (14.7)
Professional training level	
No vocational training	70 (28.6)
On-the-job training	118 (48.2)
Intermediate vocational	26 (10.6)
College-level vocational	9 (3.7)
University	22 (9.0)
Marital status	
Never married	26 (10.6)
Married and living with spouse	94 (38.4)

Characteristic	Value (N, %)
Married but not living with spouse	26 (10.6)
Separated/Divorced	80 (32.7)
Other	19 (7.8)
Residence status	
Local residents at the community/ward of the enterprise	51 (20.8)
From the same district	32 (13.1)
From the same province	81 (33.1)
From different provinces	81 (33.1)
Number of children in the family	
One child	121 (49.4)
Two children	91 (37.1)
Three children	29 (11.8)
Four children	4 (1.6)

Source: Survey results of the study

Labor policies for workers

From the perspective of female workers in special circumstances, this group reported the following wages, working hours, and support received from labor policies.

According to the General Statistics Office, in 2023, the average income of workers in Vietnam was 7.1 million VND per month. The survey results indicate that the average monthly income of female workers in industrial parks was 7.3 million VND, slightly higher than the national average. However, this salary remains insufficient to cover their daily living expenses.

A 26-year-old single mother working in Hanoi shared her experience: *“The average salary in garment and footwear companies is just over 5.5 million VND. If there is overtime, it reaches about 7 million VND. According to state regulations, salaries are adjusted once a year, but the adjustment rate has decreased. Previously, it increased by 11.3% per year, but now it is only 5.4%. This means that each increase amounts to just a few tens of thousands of VND, while the cost of worker accommodations has risen sharply. The prices of consumer goods also rise alongside wages.”*

The average working hours for female workers in this study were 8 hours per day, with an additional 12 hours of overtime per month. However, no specific data confirms the enforcement or regulation of this overtime. In contrast, a study on female garment workers in China found that they frequently endure forced and often illegal overtime, with total weekly working hours ranging between 90 and 110 hours (Chan 2006).

The table 2 highlights the challenges faced by female workers in special circumstances, focusing on three main areas: housing, income, and children’s education.

First, regarding housing challenges, many workers experience housing shortages or live in rental conditions that fail to meet their families’ minimum needs, with a mean score of 3.08 and a standard deviation of 1.34. This reflects the significant difficulty low-income workers face in securing suitable housing.

Table 2. Key challenges faced by female workers in special circumstances within industrial and export processing zones

Challenges in Life	Mean	Std
Lack of housing	3.08	1.34
Current rental housing does not meet the family's minimum needs	3.08	1.34
Income insufficient for living	3.18	0.89
No support from family	3.03	1.25
Difficulties in registering children for school due to lack of local household registration	1.98	0.93
School too far from residence	3.19	0.9
Limited quality of educational institutions	1.92	0.91
School pick-up/drop-off times incompatible with work hours	2.45	1.06
High cost of education/tutoring compared to income	2.88	1.03

Source: Survey results of the study

Beyond the housing shortage itself, the poor quality of rental accommodations further underscores the precarious living conditions of female workers in Vietnam. In a cultural context where “settling down” is seen as a prerequisite for stability and career development, access to stable housing is not just a material necessity but a foundation for the long-term well-being of individuals and families. However, many female workers are forced to accept temporary, substandard living conditions, often lacking basic amenities. This gap between actual needs and available housing options emphasizes the urgent need for targeted housing support policies for migrant and low-income workers.

As for challenges in children's education, survey data also reveals that the distance between workers' residences and schools is a major concern, significantly affecting their ability to drop off and pick up their children. This challenge not only adds to the time and financial burden of commuting but also intensifies the strain of balancing work and family responsibilities.

In addition to major challenges such as housing shortages and substandard living conditions, female workers in special circumstances also lack family support, with an average score of 3.03. This indicates that many of these workers must manage their finances independently to cover living expenses while simultaneously shouldering family responsibilities, particularly childcare. The absence of family support can significantly increase stress levels, negatively affecting both quality of life and work productivity.

A comparative study from Guangdong, China (Chan 2006) highlights both similarities and key differences regarding educational limitations and economic conditions. Issues such as poor job prospects in rural areas and declining agricultural prices have pushed many female workers and unemployed individuals to migrate to urban areas. Their motivations often include seeking better job opportunities, escaping arranged marriages or patriarchal oppression, resolving family conflicts, or simply desiring to experience urban life and expand their horizons.

Regarding economic challenges, insufficient income is a serious challenge for female workers in special circumstances, with an average rating of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 0.89. This issue directly affects their ability to cover basic living expenses and contributes

to long-term financial insecurity, particularly for single mothers, those with dependents, and individuals with health limitations.

The variance in survey responses suggests that the severity of financial strain depends on job position, seniority, and access to support policies. These findings highlight the urgent need for wage adjustments that align with the rising cost of living, as well as the expansion of social welfare programs to alleviate economic pressures on this vulnerable group.

The following table illustrates the level of savings for female workers in special circumstances, reflecting the financial strain under which they operate.

Table 3. Living conditions of female workers in special circumstances within industrial and export processing zones (Unit: %)

Accumulation Status	Quantity	Percentage
Savings	13	5.3
Sufficient for Living Expenses	59	24.1
Must Be Frugal and Save	100	40.8
Require Support from Relatives	36	14.7
Must Borrow from Credit Services	32	13.1
Other	5	2.0

Source: Survey results of the study

Overall, a significant proportion of female workers, particularly single mothers and those with serious illnesses, are forced to practice frugality, with 40.8% indicating the need to “be frugal and save”. Additionally, 14.7% of these workers reported requiring financial support from relatives.

In terms of financial coping mechanisms, 60.8% of respondents indicated that they had borrowed money to cover living expenses in the past five years. The amounts borrowed vary significantly among single mothers and those with serious health issues. Specifically, 40.1% of respondents borrowed between 20 to 30 million VND each time, 16.1% borrowed less than 10 million VND, and 10.2% borrowed 50 million VND per loan. The borrowing capacity of these workers is largely constrained by their limited repayment ability, savings, and income.

The relationship between borrowing behavior and the financial status of female workers over the past five years shows a clear connection between individual circumstances and financial needs. Among single mothers, 55.8% have taken out loans, while 44.2% have not engaged in borrowing. The borrowing rate is notably higher among women with severe illnesses, with 65.2% having borrowed money, compared to only 34.8% who have not. In the group of female workers facing the dual challenges of single motherhood and serious illness, the borrowing rate is 100%. This suggests that the financial burden on this group is significantly higher, making borrowing nearly essential for meeting basic living requirements. The data indicate that single parenthood and medical expenses are significant barriers to the financial independence of female workers, highlighting the urgent need for effective financial support policies to alleviate the burden on vulnerable groups.

The living conditions of single mother workers and those with serious illnesses are starkly reflected in their housing situations, which remain a critical aspect of their overall quality of life.

Figure 1. Housing conditions of female workers in special circumstances within industrial and export processing zones (Unit: %). *Source:* Survey results of the study

The majority of female workers in the study, accounting for 55.1%, live with their parents. Another 26.9% reside in rental accommodations, which are generally in poor condition in the country.

An analysis of the relationship between borrowing behavior for daily expenses over the past five years and housing type reveals notable disparities in borrowing rates across different groups. Female workers residing in rented accommodations exhibit the highest borrowing rate, at 83.3%, indicating significant financial instability and challenges in managing living expenses without familial support. Homeowners report a borrowing rate of 60.6%, likely due to housing-related costs such as maintenance expenses and mortgage obligations.

In contrast, female workers residing rent-free with relatives or acquaintances, as well as those living in company dormitories, show notably lower borrowing rates of 25.0% and 33.3%, respectively. This suggests that reduced housing expenses – through support from family or employers – substantially alleviate the need for borrowing to cover living costs. Women living with their parents report a borrowing rate of 52.6%, reflecting a compromise between lower living expenses and other financial obligations.

The data indicate that housing type significantly influences borrowing behavior, with borrowing tendencies increasing among those facing higher living costs and insufficient support from family or employers.

In terms of housing expenditures, 63.1% of female workers spend between 1 to 2 million dong per month on housing. A smaller group, 10.8%, spends less than 1 million dong per

month. These figures highlight the low standard of living and the significant challenges faced by female workers in managing daily life due to substandard housing conditions.

Housing difficulties are also a major challenge for female workers, as highlighted by an in-depth interview with a single mother:

“Currently, my job is suitable and stable, but because I have to spend too much money as a single mother raising two young children for school, it is very difficult financially. I have social insurance paid by the company and can access medical treatment through health insurance. However, I still struggle with housing. I don’t have the means to afford my own home, so my children and I are staying with relatives. The transportation we use to get my children to school and myself to work is very rudimentary. I also face difficulty this year because tuition fees for both children have increased.”

Given these challenging living conditions, 45% of female workers opt to send their children to public kindergartens and nurseries run by the state, reflecting their reliance on more accessible and presumably affordable childcare options.

Figure 2. Types of childcare facilities used by female workers for their children (Unit: %). *Source:* Survey results of the study

Among the childcare options available, a significant number of female workers resort to using family-run groups or private nurseries. However, this choice often generates a sense of insecurity among workers due to concerns about the quality of care. Despite their prevalence, these facilities are utilized by less than 50% of workers, who instead opt for state-run public kindergartens and nurseries.

A significant proportion of female workers rely on family members, such as grandparents or other relatives, to care for their children. This arrangement presents additional challenges, particularly from an educational perspective. When children are primarily cared for by family members, they often have limited interaction with their mothers. This infrequent contact can lead to deficiencies in care, guidance, and supervision from both parents. Consequently, children may receive less affection and fewer opportunities to develop life skills as they grow.

An examination of the relationship between the income levels of female workers and their childcare arrangements reveals clear patterns among different income groups, as illustrated in the table 4.

Public preschools and kindergartens operated by the state are the predominant choice for workers earning less than 5 million VND monthly, comprising 46.2% of this group. Child-

Table 4. Relationship between female workers' income and childcare type (Unit: %)

Childcare form	Average monthly income of female workers in special circumstances		
	Less than 5 million/month	From 5 to 10 million/Over 10 million/month	Over 10 million/month
State public kindergartens and nurseries	46.2	29.3	12.5
Company-operated kindergartens and nurseries	0.0	11.7	50.0
Family-run groups, private nurseries	38.5	25.9	12.5
Sent to grandparents or relatives in hometown for care	15.4	31.2	25.0
Domestic help	0.0	2.0	0.0

Source: Survey results of the study

care facilities managed by enterprises or trade unions are notably favored by middle-income workers, with a preference rate of 11.7%, and are particularly prevalent among individuals earning over 10 million VND monthly, at 50%. This suggests that higher-income workers are more willing to pay a premium for higher-quality childcare services provided by enterprises or trade unions.

Home-based childcare groups and private daycare centers are preferred by low-income (38.5%) and middle-income (25.9%) workers, with this preference significantly decreasing among high-income workers (12.5%). Lower- and middle-income groups may prioritize private daycare centers for their affordability and flexibility compared to public institutions, while higher-income groups likely favor facilities that meet higher quality standards.

For workers earning between 5 and 10 million VND per month, sending children back to their hometowns for care by grandparents or relatives is the predominant option, accounting for 31.2% of cases. This decision likely stems from the need to reduce childcare expenses and the availability of familial support.

The analysis reveals distinct variations in childcare choices based on income levels. Low-income workers typically opt for public daycare centers or private childcare services, while middle-income workers are more inclined to send their children back to their hometowns for care. High-income workers, on the other hand, tend to favor childcare centers operated by enterprises or trade unions, and also choose to have their children cared for by relatives in their hometowns. This variation highlights the influence of economic conditions on childcare choices among workers in industrial zones.

The data table reveals that the highest percentage of workers are affected by cancer (18.7%), followed by rheumatoid arthritis (16.3%). The study indicates that female workers who are single mothers or experience serious illnesses face significant challenges in their daily lives. The following detailed interviews illustrate their difficulties:

"My current salary is stable and sufficient to cover rent, utilities, and daily necessities." I experienced a mild stroke and currently need home treatment, physical therapy, and acupuncture, along with daily assistance from family members. My employer has adjusted my responsibilities by assigning me tasks that are appropriate for individuals with significant health issues.

Table 5. Health conditions of single mother workers/seriously ill workers in industrial and processing zones (Unit: %)

Health Conditions	Quantity	Percentage (%)
Cancer	38	18.7
Heart diseases	14	6.9
Lung diseases	6	3.0
Liver/Kidney failure	6	3.0
Rheumatoid arthritis	33	16.3
Surgeries (heart, liver, kidney, artery, spinal cord, nerves)	5	2.5
No diseases mentioned above	109	53.7

Source: Survey results of the study

The company offers limited financial assistance to employees facing difficulties. Despite the availability of annual health check-ups, my deteriorating health has adversely impacted my job performance and income.

“While my employment is stable, I seek opportunities to enhance my income or obtain partial reimbursement for commuting expenses, given that my base salary is relatively low.” Due to my child’s young age, I incur significant expenses related to milk, daycare, and preschool fees. As a single mother, I am compelled to take time off work when my child is ill, as I lack support during such times. Occasionally, despite being unwell, I am required to fulfill work obligations. As a single mother, falling ill results in a lack of support.”

“I am presently experiencing financial difficulties.” Despite having stable employment, my salary is inadequate to meet expenses due to the high tuition fees associated with my child’s education. My child is currently attending university, which exacerbates financial strain, and I lack supplementary income sources. As a single mother residing with my elderly parents, I am responsible for their care due to their retirement from work. I possess social insurance, enabling access to healthcare via the health insurance system. My aging parents often experience health issues, necessitating a balance between work, caregiving, and personal well-being.”

The in-depth interviews reveal the challenging circumstances faced by female workers, particularly those with significant health issues or those who are single mothers. They experience financial strain due to health problems and familial obligations. Employers may accommodate workers with declining health by assigning lighter tasks to ensure stable earnings, and companies often provide periodic health check-ups and limited financial assistance. However, long-term medical costs and the need for family care continue to pose significant challenges that affect their quality of life.

Single mothers face direct income disruption when they take leave to care for a sick child or lack childcare support. The absence of family support during illness necessitates independent management, which exacerbates both financial and psychological stress. Despite their employment being classified as “stable,” these persistent pressures create a precarious situation. The burden is significantly greater for individuals who care for elderly parents, as they must provide for both their children and aging family members simultaneously. Their own illness further diminishes work efficiency and negatively impacts earnings due to insufficient support.

Research from China and the Philippines has documented that female workers are prone to occupational diseases such as menstrual disorders, back pain, headaches, kidney failure, and respiratory issues (Lu 2008). In Vietnam, emerging data highlights occupational diseases among workers, including lung diseases, liver and kidney failure, and cancer. The health survey of the worker group in this study indicates that 18.7% of the workers are suffering from cancer, while 16.3% are affected by rheumatoid arthritis.

The effectiveness of employment and income support measures for female workers in this study is detailed in the table below.

Table 6. Assessment of the effectiveness of enterprise support for female workers in terms of employment and income (Unit: %)

Enterprises support for female workers in special circumstances	Effectiveness	
	Female Workers	Union Officials
Support in vocational training, job transition for female workers	47.3	43.7
Support for employment suitable to health conditions	48.1	45.1
Support for female workers in special circumstances when unemployed/underemployed	41.0	41.5
Support in creating opportunities and working conditions to enhance productivity for female workers in special circumstances	40.3	45.1
Support in creating opportunities and working conditions to increase income for female workers in special circumstances	40	41.5

Source: Survey results of the study

In the survey, 47.3% of female workers rated the effectiveness of “support in vocational training and job transition” as high, while 48.1% evaluated the support for “employment suitable to health conditions” as effective. This reflects a humane management approach among the surveyed business owners, aligning with the Vietnamese value of prioritizing relationships. Arranging work that accommodates the health conditions of employees ensures they have suitable jobs and income relative to their circumstances.

Comparatively, the union officials' assessments closely align with those of the female workers, with 43.2% rating the effectiveness similarly. There is consistency in the evaluations by both union officials and female workers regarding the effectiveness of enterprise support in training and employment for female workers with special circumstances in industrial and processing zones. However, the data shows that workers tend to rate the effectiveness of each indicator lower than union officials, likely because workers' perceptions are based on more direct and immediate experiences. Additional findings from surveys with union officials indicate that enterprises are also supporting workers by “increasing overtime pay and allowances” for female workers with special circumstances. A significant 53.5% of union officials rated the effectiveness of increasing overtime pay for female workers as “very effective.”

Access to social welfare services

Social welfare services are crucial to the quality of life for people in general. For female workers with special circumstances, these services are even more vital. The group of female workers in this study includes single mothers and those suffering from serious illnesses. For these individuals, social welfare services hold even greater significance. The results of the survey on the status of access to social welfare services by this group of workers are presented as follows.

Table 7. Challenges in accessing healthcare for single mother workers/ seriously ill workers in industrial and processing zones (Unit: %)

Challenges in accessing healthcare	Quantity	Percentage (%)
Complex procedures for health insurance examinations	39	15.9
Hospitals too far from home	56	22.9
Healthcare staff indifferent to patients using health insurance	36	14.7
Medications covered by health insurance not meeting treatment needs	98	40
No family members available to care for children when sick	100	40.8
High healthcare costs relative to income	132	53.9
Lack of time/health to care for family	120	49

Source: Survey results of the study

Accessing healthcare presents significant challenges for female workers with special circumstances. Among the respondents, 39% reported that “health insurance examination procedures are complex,” making it difficult for them to undergo health-related medical examinations. This complexity extends to purchasing medication outside of hospitals, where patients seeking reimbursement through health insurance must navigate a confusing array of receipts, documents, and administrative procedures on their own, rather than receiving support from doctors and healthcare staff, as they would within a hospital setting. Additionally, the issue of “medications covered by health insurance not meeting treatment needs” further complicates the situation for these workers, especially when faced with high treatment costs.

Furthermore, 53.9% of the workers surveyed highlighted difficulties with “high healthcare costs compared to income.” This situation underscores the struggles faced by female workers with special circumstances, whose incomes are often only sufficient to cover basic living expenses. The additional financial burden of medications and healthcare exacerbates their precarious financial situation. This burden impacts not just the individual family but also the extended family, who often must pool resources to care for an ill member, leading many families to fall into poverty once again.

Consequently, the cycle of poverty and illness continues to deeply affect the working class. With already limited incomes and the necessity for frugality, these workers also grapple with ongoing medical expenses, with some survey respondents indicating that they had to borrow money to cover their expenditures.

The various borrowing options accessed by female workers are detailed in the graph below (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Sources of loans for female workers in special circumstances in industrial and processing zones (Unit: %). *Source:* Survey results of the study

In the survey, 56.7% of respondents reported that they primarily borrow from “relatives and friends,” which is seen as the most accessible network for female workers. This indicates that personal networks are the most dependable financial resource for vulnerable workers, due to their flexibility, minimal risk, and the absence of complicated requirements compared to borrowing from banks or financial institutions. However, dependence on informal lending sources poses certain risks, especially when the financial resources of family and friends are limited. This reliance increases the risk of financial crises when borrowing needs exceed the support capacity of personal networks.

Bank loans were utilized by 27.8% of the participants, demonstrating that some workers have access to mainstream financial sources offering reasonable interest rates. Loans from union organizations were also noted, though less frequently, at 8.2%, suggesting that unions provide some financial support to female workers during times of difficulty.

Although only 1.2% of the workers surveyed acknowledged accessing “predatory loans,” the actual prevalence of such borrowing could be higher within the broader working community. Predatory loans attract borrowers due to their speed and minimal procedural requirements, but the consequences of these loans are often severe and unforeseen.

Workers often resort to predatory loans for essential needs, such as family living expenses, housing costs, children’s tuition fees, personal desires, and medical treatments for relatives, including sending money home or purchasing transportation. Regardless of the reason, the consequences of these loans are severe, making workers poorer, more unstable, and anxious due to the excessively high interest rates, which often exceed their ability to repay. This situation highlights a gap in the formal credit system, which cannot fully address the urgent financial needs of vulnerable female workers. Limited access to credit from banks, trade unions, or formal financial institutions forces some workers into a deadlock, leaving them with no choice but to accept the risks of illegal lending.

Research conducted by Dang Thi Kim Phuong and Phan Dinh Khoi (2022) identifies factors such as employment status, participation frequency in meetings, income level, and ethnicity as key determinants of women’s access to microcredit. Women in stable employment have better access to microcredit, owing to their steady income, repayment ability, and established reputation within the community. Consequently, women employed in traditionally stable sectors like education and healthcare generally enjoy greater access to formal

credit than those working in industrial occupations. Factory workers, in particular, often face job instability, frequent job transitions, or migrant labor.

Similarly, the female workers with special circumstances in this study face considerable obstacles in obtaining formal credit from banks or financial institutions. Employment instability and socioeconomic vulnerabilities place this group in a context of restricted financial opportunities, which leads them to rely on informal lending networks or microfinance initiatives as their primary sources of financial support.

In addition to challenges in accessing social services, female workers in this study also face difficulties accessing recreational activities, as detailed in the following survey results.

Table 8. Challenges in accessing recreational activities for single mother workers/seriously ill workers in industrial and processing zones (Unit: %)

Challenges in recreational activities	Quantity	Percentage (%)
Parks and cultural houses far from residence	43	36.8
Lack of funds for recreational activities	20	17.1
No cultural houses or parks in the worker's area	38	32.5
No recreational or sports facilities for workers	28	23.9
High cost of accessing recreational facilities compared to income	15	12.8

Source: Survey results of the study

Mental well-being is a crucial aspect that revitalizes the labor force of individuals, including female workers. Various forms of entertainment can enhance mental health, but female workers face significant challenges in accessing these resources. Common barriers include: "Parks and cultural centers being far from their residences", "No cultural houses or parks in the worker's area", "High costs of accessing recreational facilities relative to income", and "Lack of funds for recreational activities."

When comparing the two groups of female workers, those with serious illnesses experience more financial strain when it comes to leisure activities than single mothers. Specifically, 60.2% of female workers with significant health issues reported difficulties in affording recreational activities, compared to 43.7% of single mothers. This suggests that illness has a more profound impact on the financial capacity of female workers than single parenthood, as healthcare expenses and reduced work capacity likely affect their economic stability to a greater extent.

Support from the Government and Enterprises for Female Workers in Special Circumstances

The support provided by the state to female workers with special circumstances is another important area investigated in this study. The results are presented below (table 9).

The evaluations from female workers in special circumstances highlight the effectiveness of state support. Vocational training and job transition support are rated as relatively effective by 51% of respondents, while 56.8% consider employment support that accommodates health conditions to be effective.

State-provided housing support for female workers in special circumstances has an effectiveness rating of 36.7%, with 13.8% of respondents considering it "very effective."

Table 9. Effectiveness of state support for female workers (Unit: %)

Support Type	Very Ineffective	Ineffective	Average	Effective	Very Effective
Vocational training and job transition support for female workers	5.1	12.6	31.3	37.4	13.6
Support for employment suitable to health	4.7	9.9	28.6	46	10.8
Support for female workers in special circumstances when unemployed/underemployed	3.3	11.8	32.2	43.6	9.0
Support in creating opportunities and working conditions to enhance productivity and income for female workers in special circumstances	4.2	7.0	36.6	38	14.1

Source: Survey results of the study

From the perspective of union officials, the state's support extends to vocational training, as well as assistance in building homes or providing dormitories, enabling workers to operate with peace of mind. Notably, for single mothers, the state facilitates opportunities for “interaction and connection,” allowing them to find suitable partners. Union officials estimate the effectiveness of this initiative at 60.8%, underscoring the state's role in fostering social interactions through networking activities between companies.

Additionally, union officials noted that the state provides preferential credit support for workers, though the effectiveness of this policy is rated lower, at just 13.8%. Furthermore, 17.6% of union officials mentioned that the state provides cultural and social information to workers, demonstrating a broader approach to supporting workers' integration and well-being beyond mere financial and employment assistance.

Table 10. Enterprise support for access to welfare for female workers in special circumstances (Unit: %)

Enterprise support for female workers	Worker ratings (% Satisfaction)
Enterprises ensure long-term stable employment	73.3
Enterprises support building individual homes	59.2
Opportunity to purchase homes at preferential prices	65.6
Provision of dormitories for workers	63.3
Childcare facilities for workers' children	15
Healthcare facilities for workers outside office hours	70.5
Cultural houses for workers	70.9
Recreational and relaxation areas after work hours	68.3
Support for travel expenses to work	73
Support for rent, utilities, and internet at rental properties	68.9

Source: Survey results of the study

The survey results also show support from enterprises for workers in general, and particularly for female workers in special circumstances. They receive support including dormitories, the opportunity to purchase homes at reduced prices, and childcare facilities for workers' children. These forms of support from enterprises reflect a humane approach to management.

However, female workers facing special circumstances show lower satisfaction levels with housing support policies compared to other types of assistance. This suggests that, although housing is a fundamental necessity, corporate policies have not fully addressed workers' expectations. Possible contributing factors include high costs, challenging accessibility, or sub-standard housing quality.

Satisfaction with childcare support is the lowest among all forms of assistance, with only 15% of workers indicating approval. This highlights a significant gap in policies that address the childcare needs of female employees, potentially due to inadequate facilities or limited corporate resources for developing daycare centers.

The findings suggest that, while housing and childcare support are essential, current policies are insufficient and need improvement to better meet the needs of female workers in special circumstances. Evaluations from union officials indicate the effectiveness of the various activities that enterprises support for female workers in special circumstances. The preferential credit support policy has an effectiveness rating of 13.8% and a very effective rating of 34.6%. The enterprise's poverty reduction support policy is rated effective at 15.1%, with 34.8% rating it as very effective. The policy supporting retirement conditions is rated as effective at 21.2%, and very effective at 38.8%.

For workers with poor health, enterprises have provided certain forms of support, as shown in the table below.

Table 11. Enterprise support for female workers in special circumstances

Enterprise Support	Mean	SD
Enterprise facilitates my job completion and income increase	3.88	0.58
Enterprise offers certain benefits to me	3.53	0.78
Enterprise provides economic support to me	3.35	0.85
Enterprise annually provides certain gifts and visits my family	3.65	0.72
Enterprise facilitates my skill enhancement	3.69	0.77

Source: Survey results of the study

The support provided by enterprises for female workers with special circumstances is demonstrated in the table above. Notably, the support that helps female workers complete their tasks and increase their income scores quite highly, at 3.88 out of 5. This reflects the level of attention enterprises pay to female workers, as well as their efforts to assist in enhancing income and improving material well-being.

A significant observation is that enterprises also help female workers enhance their skills. Improving skills not only boosts labor productivity but also results in a more skilled workforce for the enterprise. From a management perspective, this indicates that enterprises have provided meaningful support to female workers with special circumstances.

An analysis of the relationship between the educational background of female workers in special circumstances and their satisfaction with the indicator "Enterprise support for

skills and professional development” reveals that most workers report being satisfied or very satisfied. The cohort undergoing vocational training within the enterprise exhibited the highest level of agreement (67.0%), while those with vocational college degrees demonstrated the lowest satisfaction (28.6%), suggesting potentially limited opportunities for further skill development.

A notable percentage of workers maintained a neutral stance, comprising 29.3%. The greatest level of neutrality was observed among vocational college graduates (71.4%), followed by university graduates (45.5%) and intermediate vocational graduates (44.0%). This trend suggests that organizations should revise their training policies to provide equitable opportunities for professional development across various educational groups, thereby addressing disparities in access to skill enhancement programs.

Discussions

This study provides a comprehensive examination of the lives of female workers in Vietnam's industrial zones, highlighting the unique challenges they face, which are often exacerbated by their special circumstances. Despite the array of support systems from businesses, government, and non-governmental organizations, our findings indicate that these efforts are insufficient to fully address the needs of female workers, particularly those who are single mothers or suffer from severe illnesses and occupational diseases.

Gap in policy and practice

One of the significant insights from this research is the discrepancy between the available support and the actual needs of female workers. While policies are in place to provide healthcare, housing, and income support, their implementation often falls short of effectively reaching the intended beneficiaries. For example, healthcare services, although theoretically accessible, are hindered by complex insurance procedures and a lack of medication coverage that meets the workers' needs. Similarly, housing support does not align with the actual living conditions and financial capacities of the workers, leaving many in inadequate housing situations.

Economic strain and social welfare

The economic strain on these workers is evident from their reliance on multiple loan sources to manage daily expenses, which often exceed their incomes. This financial instability is compounded by high healthcare costs and insufficient social welfare support, driving many into a cycle of debt and poverty. The study's findings emphasize the need for targeted financial aid and more robust health insurance schemes to alleviate some of these economic pressures.

Recommendations for improvement

To address the gaps identified in this research, the authors recommend the following strategic interventions:

- Enhanced healthcare access. Simplify the health insurance processes and expand coverage to include essential medications and treatments that are currently not supported.

- Improved housing policies. Develop more inclusive housing programs that cater to the specific needs of female workers, particularly single mothers and those facing health challenges.
- Economic support. Increase access to low-interest loans and provide financial counseling for female workers to help them manage debt and avoid predatory lending practices.
- Long-term employment opportunities. Encourage businesses to create more stable job opportunities that accommodate the health and family needs of female workers. This could include options such as flexible working hours and remote work.

Conclusion and Further recommendations

This article has examined labor policies, access to social welfare, and support mechanisms from both governmental and non-governmental organizations, specifically focusing on female workers facing challenging circumstances in Vietnam. The findings reveal that many of these workers, particularly single mothers and those suffering from serious illnesses, struggle with incomes insufficient to meet basic living expenses, forcing them to rely on additional financial support from various lending sources.

For female workers with serious illnesses, the high cost of medical treatments exacerbates their financial burdens, further intensifying their struggles. Despite the existence of support from enterprises and the government, these interventions have yet to significantly improve the living conditions of these workers. Housing policies, in particular, have not adequately addressed the needs of the studied group, leaving many to cope with the compounded challenges of low income, child-rearing responsibilities, and healthcare expenses.

The study paints a stark picture of the situation faced by single mothers and female workers with serious health issues in Vietnam, highlighting the ongoing need for enhanced support from the state, businesses, and other social organizations. Collective efforts are essential to ensure that these vulnerable groups can achieve a better quality of life and more stable economic conditions.

Further research is needed to continuously evaluate the effectiveness of new policies and practices implemented in response to these recommendations. Longitudinal studies would provide deeper insights into the long-term impact of these interventions on improving the lives of female workers in industrial zones.

In conclusion, this discussion emphasizes the need for a concerted effort from all sectors of society – including policymakers, businesses, and community organizations – to implement more effective and compassionate strategies that address the specific needs of female workers with special circumstances in Vietnam. The ultimate goal is to create an environment where these workers can thrive both professionally and personally, free from the undue burdens currently placed upon them.

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